

Beyond pure R&D: setting a model in academia-industry technology transfer

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Abstract: I had the opportunity and the privilege to interact, learn and work with Prof. Nina Thornhill for a limited period of time around 2005 and 2006. Although coming from R&D, at the time I was already working for an ABB Business Unit trying to bridge the gap between fancy and sophisticated algorithms and the very pragmatic process industry world. Being deeply involved with product development and deployment, top priority had to be given to business considerations and actual market acceptance even at cost of constraining genuine innovation and engineering passion.

Keywords: PID tuning, maintain software tools, industrial academic technology transfer, optimal process operations.

My team had developed a suite of advanced process control software aiming at optimizing process operation at different levels: from basic PIDs computer-assisted tuning and performance monitoring to more ambitious multivariable control strategies operating at higher (unit) level. Our primary duty was to promote, deploy and maintain the software tools at global level and for multiple industrial sectors. Still we were feeling that more could have been added to our solutions and practices, in order to provide more process insight to our Customers and to squeeze out of the plants additional margins in terms of safety, environmental compatibility and efficiency.

The problem we had was to not only embed smart solutions in software tools but also structure them in such a way that they do not require a PhD in Statistics or Control Theory to be used but could be beneficial for a plant engineer working on the front-line at a production site.

Fig. 1. ABB's OptimizeIT Loop Performance Manager 3.0 – PDA Extension was released in 2003.

Fig. 2. The first application of the package was tested at Eastman Chemicals thanks to the competent and professional contribution of John Cox as described in [1]

We had built a strong and fruitful relationship with several ABB Corporate Research Centers, including the Ladenburg one, where Alexander Horch and his team had provided key algorithms, brain-power and support for realizing the core of our control loop assessment solutions. Given the trust, I was immediately interested when he mentioned the opportunity to meet and cooperate with Prof. Nina Thornhill and possibly incorporate in our product, algorithms developed by her and her team at Imperial College. The promise looked to me too nice to be real: being able to look at a process plant as a whole, giving rigorous yet easy to be managed indications about disturbances and about how they propagate through equipment and devices. Coupling process-wide approach and root-cause analysis with local PID assessment and inferential measurement seemed to be a quantum leap in the journey to optimal continuous process operations.

The meeting and the following cooperation with Prof. Thornhill was a really exciting experience. We had the opportunity to learn a lot about actually cool concepts and practices, always feeling comfortable in asking for more details or discussing possible software solutions able to constrain and reduce the complexity into regions manageable by the average process engineer.

Working under Nina's scientific lead, the ABB CRC colleagues and my team were finally able to embed the Plant-wide Disturbance Analysis algorithms into our product and in the spring of 2006, we could release the Loop Performance Manager 3.0 with the PDA optional addendum.

Prof. Thornhill capability to couple rigorous scientific approach and a far-reaching understanding of deployment and usability issues is still, in my experience, completely unmatched: quite a model in managing technology transfer and establishing rewarding academia-industry partnerships.

In the following years, new roles and duties drove me away from the APC arena but it is still quite an honor for me identifying in my publication list an article co-written with Prof. Thornhill (and a few other colleagues, [2]). The only regret is not to have had more opportunities to work together and to learn more from her comprehensive and smart approach.

Fig. 3. The article 'Peak performance' described the work done with Prof. N. Thornhill.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Horch, J. Cox, N. Bonavita "Peak Performance. Root cause analysis of plant-wide disturbances", *ABB Review*, 1/2007, pp. 24-29
- [2] A. Horch, V. Hegre, K. Hilmen, H. Malbo, L. Benabbas, S. Pistikopoulos, N. Thornhill, N. Bonavita "Computer-aided plant auditing made possible by successful university cooperation", *ABB Review*, 2/2005, pp. 44-48